

Effects of carbon dioxide and temperature on methane emission of rice

L. H. Allen, Jr., S. L. Albercht, W. Colón, and S. A. Covell, United States Department of Agriculture, Agricultural Research Service (USDA-ARS) and University of Florida, Gainesville, FL 32611, USA

Rice cultivation may be the largest anthropogenic source of CH₄ emission (Hogan et al 1991). Factors such as irrigation, organic matter, fertilization, temperature, and season affect emission from ricefields (Lindau et al 1990, Khalil et al 1991). The objective of this study was to determine the effects of elevated CO₂ and temperatures on CH₄ emission of tropical lowland rice grown under flooded conditions.

Rice cultivar IR72 was grown in eight outdoor, controlled environment plant growth chambers. Daytime atmospheric CO₂ was maintained at 330 (four chambers) or 660 (four chambers) µmol CO₂/mol air. Air temperature was controlled to follow a natural, diurnal, sinusoidal pattern between daily minimum and maximum temperatures of 32/23, 35/26, and 38/29 °C in each CO₂ treatment. Carbon dioxide treatments were replicated once at the 30/29 °C temperature treatment.

Preplant fertilizer (80 kg P and K/ha) was applied on 8 Jul 1992. Rice seeds, pregerminated for 4 d, were planted 20 Jul in 20- × 20-cm hills. Nitrogen was applied as urea in three split applications on 27 Jul (8 d after planting [DAP]), 20 Aug (32 DAP), and 21 Sep (64 DAP).

Soil redox potential and irrigation water pH were measured three times a week during the first two-thirds of the season and once a week thereafter. Final harvest samples were collected on 17-20 and 23 Nov (122-125 and 128 DAP).

For whole-chamber CH₄ measurements, air was pumped sequentially to a gas chromatograph with flame ionization detector. First, daily CH₄ emission was determined from the slope (mg CH₄/m² per h) of four samples measured every 27 min from about 0800 to 1000 h. Second, several times during the season, diurnal CH₄ emission rates were measured at 4-h intervals after flushing each chamber with

Methane emission (mg CH₄/m² per h) at 54, 64, 101, and 136 d after planting (DAP) taken from a hill containing 4 plants and from stubble at 136 DAP after the plant shoots were cut at 5 cm and removed.

DAP	CO ₂ concentration (µmol/mol)					
	330			660		
	32 °C	35 °C	38 °C	32 °C	35 °C	38 °C
54	1.5	1.2	1.0	0.7	0.6	1.6
64	2.2	0.9	3.1	1.9	2.0	6.1
101	7.1	2.9	3.4	6.5	7.8	13.3
136	4.4	4.1	9.2	3.2	12.6	16.1
136 Stubble	4.7	3.9	8.1	3.7	9.8	15.2

outside air. Third, several times during the season, CH₄ was measured using closed PVC tubes placed over plants, bare soil, or plant stubble. Methane emissions were determined from the slope of four to five air samples taken by syringe every 10 min.

Daily methane efflux was small up to 40 DAP, although all deep platinum electrodes registered -200 mV by 24 Aug (36 DAP). Methane emission increased soon afterward, with the highest rates observed from the high CO₂ and high temperature treatments. Soil-water samples taken at the end of the season at 5 cm showed little CH₄ at 32, 35, and 38 °C, but at the 17 cm depth, CH₄ content decreased with increased air temperature. Analysis of variance (model R² = 0.97) showed a significant CO₂, temperature, and DAP effect on daily CH₄ efflux (P < 0.001), and a significant interaction between CO₂ × temperature, CO₂ × DAP, and temperature × DAP (P < 0.001).

Diurnal methane efflux from the whole canopy was obtained at 78, 99, 121, and 139 DAP (data not shown). Greatest methane efflux was from 0800 to 1000 h, followed by a gradual decline with minimal rates at 2000-2400 h. At 78 DAP, diurnal methane efflux was greater at the highest CO₂ (660 µmol/mol) and temperature (38 °C) treatment, with no differences among the other five combinations. By 99 DAP, diurnal methane efflux was greatest in the high CO₂ treatments regardless of temperature. Diurnal effluxes at 121 DAP with full canopy and those at 139 DAP with stubble were similar.

Methane efflux was measured from hills with plants and adjacent bare soil-water surfaces at 54, 64, 101, and 136 DAP (see table). Effluxes from the bare surfaces were very low (data not shown) compared with the vegetated surfaces.

Emissions clearly increased with increasing CO₂, temperature, and DAP. Methane efflux was very similar between the plants and stubble (see table). Emissions from the stubble plants were obtained about 1 h after clipping the canopy to 5 cm above the water level.

Methane effluxes may be related to plant or root biomass (Sass et al 1990) and photosynthetic rate (Whiting et al 1991). Baker and Allen (1993) pointed out that CO₂ enrichment increased rice photosynthesis, total aboveground biomass, root biomass, tillering, and final grain yield. Since root exudate may be more than 1.7% of photosynthate (Feldman 1988), the increase in methane efflux may be because of higher soil substrate levels obtained under high CO₂. Tiller number, photosynthetic rates, and root biomass seem likely to exert a significant role in increasing CH₄ emission.

In summary, these data are the first to show a direct relationship between increased atmospheric CO₂ concentration and CH₄ emission in a flooded rice-culture environment.

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